

Chemical and Hydrolysis Resistance of Glass Fortified Thermoplastic Resins

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Eighteen polymers and polymer composites are compared in a number of chemical environments under conditions typically encountered by molded thermoplastics. The resulting data show that glass reinforced thermoplastic resins have better chemical resistance than their unreinforced base resins. Trends are established that can be used to predict chemical resistance of composites and polymers in other environments.

STRENGTH, stiffness, and other mechanical properties of almost all thermoplastics can be doubled and even tripled by proper incorporation of fillers and reinforcement. Short term, high temperature performance, commonly measured by deflection temperature, is also greatly increased by fiber reinforcement. These performance advantages, coupled with economies and advantages of injection molding production, have opened many new application areas for thermoplastics.

The increased use of thermoplastic composites in aggressive environments has generated the need to evaluate their long term performance reliability. Little experimental data are available in which polymers or polymer composites commonly used in engineering applications are compared under similar conditions. Furthermore, no uniform method of applying experimental data obtained for one resin in a given chemical environment has been established for predicting the effects of the same environment on a different resin. Also, the effects of water on polymer composites have been overlooked. The design engineer should carefully consider the type and length of exposure and use these data along with cost and physical property requirements in materials selection.

Chemical Resistance

One difficulty encountered in a chemical resistance testing program is that of establishing meaningful test parameters. In this study, changes in tensile strength of

both unstrained and strained samples at room temperature and at elevated temperature were defined as the most important parameters for study.

ASTM D 1822 type tensile impact samples were used with five bars tested for each chemical environment. A control sample was tested and tensile strength calculated. At the end of a week (168 ± 1 hr) at 23 ± 2 C, the test bars were removed from the chemical environment. Excess liquid was wiped from the specimens, and they were weighed and tested within 2 hrs of removal. Values on strained samples were obtained by positioning the same type of bars in an arced jig which applied 1/4% flexural strain. These samples were immersed and removed from the chemical environment with the unstrained samples.

Elevated temperature chemical resistance was obtained by immersing unstrained test bars in the various environments at 81 ± 2 C for $72 \pm 1/2$ hrs. If the boiling point of the solvent was below 81 C, the test was run at the solvent's boiling point. Tensile strength values reported in Tables 1 and 2 are accurate to ± 50 psi.

If a polymer or polymer composite lost less than 3% tensile strength, it was judged excellent (E). In some cases, an actual increase in tensile strength was observed and attributed in part to stress relief. The number of test bars exhibiting tensile strength gain was much lower in the strained specimens. Materials with a tensile strength loss between 3 and 10% were judged acceptable (A). The chemical resistance of polymers for which losses between 10 and 25% were observed were judged fair (F). Long range resistance properties for this category are minimal, but short range resistance properties are sufficient to allow exposure during fabrication or other one time operations. Materials with a tensile strength loss over 25% were considered unacceptable (X) for contact with the environment indicated, regardless of length of exposure.

Because most glass reinforced thermoplastics are used at normal ambient temperatures, the room temperature data for tensile strength change provide a basis for analysis

TABLE 1 — Chemical Resistance of

Base Resin	—Glass Filler— (% wt) (% vol)		Initial Tensile Strength	Hydrochloric Acid, 10%	Sulfuric Acid, 10%	Acetic Acid	Ammonium Hydroxide	Heptane	Ethylene Glycol
ABS	30	14.9	19,000	F 11 16,100	A 4 17,960	A 5 17,880	F 7 15,560	F 9 17,920	E 8 19,080
				F 7 16,660	F 10 15,300	F 11 14,820	X 12 11,340	A 10 17,540	A 10 18,070
SAN	30	15.4	17,400	F 9 14,830	F 6 15,260	F 11 14,230	X 11 12,700	E 3 17,570	E 3 18,240
				F 11 13,730	F 9 14,080	F 11 13,570	F 7 13,570	E 6 17,170	F 14 15,420
Polystyrene	30	15.0	12,500	F 13 10,350	X 14 8,830	X 15 8,710	X 12 6,930	A 9 1,780	A 14 11,490
				X 13 8,460	X 13 8,460	X 14 7,530	X 11 7,930	A 17 D	F 17 9,950
Polycarbonate	30	16.8	18,500	A 5 17,560	F 9 16,130	A 8 17,060	X 15 9,030	A 12 16,890	E 9 18,540
				A 5 17,460	A 4 16,800	A 5 16,760	X 16 8,230	A 7 17,820	F 16 14,780
Polyethylene	0	0	8,300	A 4 7,890	A 3 7,860	A 6 7,480	X 17 2,570	F 14 7,370	F 15 7,310
				A 6 7,820	F 6 6,920	A 6 7,480	X 17 2,570	A 9 7,820	A 11 7,870
Polysulfone	30	13.9	10,000	F 11 8,470	F 10 8,490	F 13 7,920	X 16 4,670	F 16 8,150	E 12 9,710
				F 8 8,240	F 8 8,220	F 9 7,850	X 15 4,580	X 15 6,430	A 9 9,660
Polysulfone	30	17.3	18,000	F 8 15,880	F 7 15,750	A 9 16,220	F 10 13,930	A 8 17,460	E 7 18,200
				X 14 11,680	F 11 13,730	F 7 14,400	F 9 13,820	A 12 16,520	E 7 17,780
Polyacetal	30	19.2	13,000	F 14 10,750	F 13 10,050	F 10 10,860	F 9 10,210	E 2 13,160	F 16 11,350
				F 12 10,100	X 14 7,900	F 13 10,100	X 10 9,450	A 8 12,260	A 12 12,300
Polypropylene	0	0	8,200	E 2 8,200	X 13 3,610	E 1 7,870	E 1 3,220	E 1 8,270	E 4 8,310
				E 1 8,130	X 15 4,690	E 1 8,170	E 1 8,260	E 1 8,160	E 2 8,290
Polypropylene	30	13.2	7,800	A 5 7,400	A 5 7,320	A 4 7,430	A 4 7,300	X 18 3,500	E 2 8,280
				F 8 6,840	A 3 7,320	A 6 7,030	A 4 6,990	X 16 3,530	E 4 7,900
Nylon 6	30	16.1	23,000	X 18 9,360	X 17 10,630	X 18 11,250	X 14 11,640	A 9 21,690	E 10 22,560
				X 17 11,780	X 18 10,510	X 17 10,880	X 14 11,730	E 5 22,750	E 6 22,770
Nylon 6/10	30	15.4	21,000	F 15 17,070	F 11 16,860	F 14 16,360	F 8 16,720	E 3 21,210	E 10 20,600
				F 10 16,840	F 7 17,330	F 10 16,420	F 8 16,360	E 3 21,020	E 8 20,660
Nylon 6/6	30	16.1	26,000	X 17 14,200	X 16 14,510	X 17 14,200	X 13 13,570	A 13 23,530	F 17 21,090
				X 16 14,430	X 16 14,980	X 16 14,200	X 13 13,620	F 13 23,060	F 15 22,200
Thermoplastic Polyurethane	0	0	11,800	X 16 7,820	X 15 7,710	X 16 7,580	X 18 2,500	X 17 8,370	X 18 7,120
				X 15 7,620	X 17 6,400	X 14 7,290	X 18 2,500	F 14 8,970	X 18 7,670
PVC	30	17.4	8,200	F 10 6,960	F 8 7,170	F 12 6,630	F 6 6,900	E 3 8,280	E 1 8,850
				F 9 6,720	F 5 6,940	F 8 6,500	F 6 6,450	E 2 8,330	E 1 8,630
PVC	15	9.1	16,000	E 3 15,840	E 1 15,900	A 2 15,490	E 3 15,540	E 7 15,840	E 6 16,220
				E 3 15,860	E 1 15,700	A 2 15,490	E 3 15,570	E 4 15,840	E 3 16,300
Thermoplastic Polyester	30	18.8	19,500	A 7 17,860	F 12 15,420	A 7 18,040	F 5 17,060	E 6 19,680	A 13 18,040
				A 4 18,450	F 12 14,780	A 4 17,920	F 5 16,670	E 2 19,810	F 13 17,470
Modified PPO	30	15.2	21,000	E 1 21,740	A 2 20,310	A 3 20,200	E 2 21,570	F 15 17,620	E 5 21,800
				E 2 21,150	A 2 19,760	A 3 19,760	E 2 21,210	A 11 19,320	E 5 21,190

The three columns under each chemical listed consist of: 1. A letter-grade, ranking the resistance of the material to the chemical. (See key at right.) 2. A numerical ranking of the material/chemical combination, based on the materials tested. (Number 1 in each column has the highest resistance to the specific chemical.)

3. Tensile strength of the material (psi), tested after exposure to the chemical for seven days at room temperature. Values in light type are for unstrained samples; values shown in bold type are for materials exposed to the chemicals under an applied strain, in flexure, of ¼%.

of chemical resistance at "average" conditions. If the application requires only that the thermoplastic be self supporting, the data for unstrained tensile change should be consulted. The data on tensile strength change for samples at 1/4% strain offer more utility, however, for most engineering applications.

In addition to the larger losses in tensile strength of strained specimens, other, more specific trends can be observed. If the chemical resistance of a material is judged excellent or acceptable when unstrained, the additional

tensile strength loss for the material under strain is generally from 0 to 5%. Thus, most of the glass fortified thermoplastics judged excellent or acceptable unstrained remain excellent or acceptable strained. On the other hand, thermoplastics with marginal or unacceptable resistance generally lose an additional 5 to 15% of tensile strength when strained. For example, 30% glass reinforced ABS has excellent resistance to ethylene glycol unstrained; the value of tensile strength is 19,080 psi. Subjected to 1/4% strain, a 5% additional loss to 18,080 psi is observed. The same

TABLE 2 — Chemical Resistance of Reinforced Resins at Elevated Temperature

Base Resin	Hydrochloric Acid, 10%	Ammonium Hydroxide, 10%	Ethylene Glycol	Methanol†	Linseed Oil	Clorox	Cascade, 10%	Gasoline
ABS	F 7 15,220	X 6 13,410	F 7 16,850	X 9 13,360	F 10 15,890	X 10 13,250	X 10 12,820	X 11 6,050
Polystyrene	F 8 9,850	X 9 5,010	F 9 10,690	X 13 2,760	X 10 8,870	F 9 9,410	X 9 8,760	X 12 D
Polycarbonate	F 3 16,510	X 12 C	A 4 17,460	X 8 13,130	F 6 16,180	A 4 16,210	F 8 15,370	F 5 15,800
Polycarbonate*	A 2 7,690	X 12 C	F 8 7,290	F 5 7,010	F 11 6,910	F 6 6,860	F 7 7,180	X 9 5,830
Polyethylene	F 6 8,190	X 7 5,820	A 6 9,240	F 3 8,720	F 7 8,580	F 7 8,180	A 3 9,160	X 7 7,160
Polysulfone	F 5 14,770	F 5 14,010	E 3 18,020	F 4 15,650	F 7 15,440	A 3 16,420	F 5 15,680	X 8 12,730
Polyacetal	X 11 C	F 4 10,200	F 10 10,800	F 7 9,900	A 4 11,870	F 5 11,390	F 5 11,330	F 3 11,500
Polyacetal*	X 11 C	E 1 8,570	E 2 8,460	E 1 8,200	E 2 8,200	A 2 7,640	E 1 8,240	E 1 8,280
Polypropylene	F 4 6,440	F 3 6,990	A 5 7,280	F 6 6,450	F 5 6,900	F 8 6,110	A 4 7,120	X 10 4,570
Nylon 6/10	X 9 8,850	X 8 9,270	X 11 15,230	X 10 12,340	A 3 20,110	X 11 11,710	X 11 13,010	A 2 19,740
Nylon 6/6	X 10 1,850	X 10 8,450	X 12 15,210	X 11 12,700	F 9 22,000	X 12 11,860	X 13 11,000	F 6 22,200
Nylon 6/6*	X 11 C	X 11 2,510	X 13 4,370	X 12 4,650	X 12 8,440	X 13 4,460	X 12 5,570	F 4 10,250
Modified PPO	E 1 21,000	A 2 19,250	E 1 21,840	E 2 20,440	E 1 21,700	E 1 21,650	A 2 20,300	X 12 D

See footnotes, Table 1, for description of information in columns. Tensile strength values listed above were measured after exposure

to the indicated chemicals for 72 hr at 180 F (81 C). *Unreinforced resins. †Test temperature, 65 C.

Reinforced Resins at Room Temperature

Methanol		Linseed Oil		Mazola Corn Oil		Clorox		Kester #1544 Flux		Lestoll, 2%		Gasoline		Motor Oil		Brake Fluid	
X 14	13,360	E 4	18,960	A 9	18,410	A 7	17,290	A 7	18,240	F 6	16,150	X 16	5,950	F 10	17,020	X 17	10,130
X 16	7,600	F 14	16,700	F 15	16,550	F 8	16,490	F 13	16,060	X 12	12,330	X 15	5,150	F 13	16,660	X 16	1,250
X 18	3,240	E 8	17,210	E 3	18,040	F 12	14,760	A 8	16,550	F 8	13,570	X 12	13,000	X 18	12,950	X 18	6,070
X 18	2,630	E 5	16,970	E 4	17,470	F 13	13,940	F 15	13,470	X 10	12,150	X 16	D	F 15	14,340	X 17	D
X 16	7,230	F 17	10,330	A 16	11,360	F 12	10,600	A 10	11,790	X 15	6,740	X 17	D	F 14	10,530	F 9	10,550
X 17	3,240	F 17	9,480	A 13	11,390	X 15	9,310	F 12	10,600	X 18	5,550	X 16	D	X 18	6,400	X 17	D
F 9	15,950	A 14	16,890	E 5	19,000	A 5	17,230	A 11	17,190	F 16	16,150	F 9	15,060	F 15	15,370	F 14	14,100
F 10	16,480	A 11	16,890	F 14	14,820	F 10	15,630	A 7	17,950	F 4	15,520	F 8	14,710	F 17	14,760	X 12	13,320
A 7	7,710	A 15	7,520	A 13	7,910	A 6	7,670	A 6	8,010	E 2	8,230	F 8	6,800	F 12	7,200	F 11	6,670
A 7	7,610	F 13	7,400	A 10	7,690	A 8	7,520	E 4	8,210	E 2	8,200	X 10	5,940	F 14	7,180	X 14	2,820
A 6	9,330	A 10	9,750	A 12	9,570	F 15	8,200	A 13	9,250	X 11	6,780	F 11	7,510	E 4	9,780	A 6	9,520
F 9	8,960	A 10	9,430	A 9	9,480	F 12	8,060	F 10	8,960	X 13	6,460	X 9	7,370	E 6	9,710	A 6	9,430
A 8	16,380	A 13	16,690	A 10	17,390	F 10	15,480	E 5	17,710	F 16	15,710	X 14	8,100	E 5	17,510	X 15	13,410
A 6	16,580	F 12	16,150	A 11	16,560	F 7	16,000	A 9	16,600	X 8	13,360	X 14	7,940	E 4	17,950	X 13	12,710
F 10	10,560	E 1	13,850	E 8	12,810	F 9	11,480	A 12	12,050	F 4	11,260	E 2	13,000	E 1	14,000	E 1	13,900
F 11	9,750	A 8	12,300	A 12	11,860	F 14	10,350	E 6	12,750	F 6	10,500	E 2	12,950	E 1	13,900	E 3	13,100
E 4	7,840	E 2	8,200	E 4	8,240	E 1	8,290	E 2	8,080	E 1	8,100	E 1	8,210	E 2	8,420	E 2	8,390
E 4	7,870	E 1	8,260	E 3	8,180	E 2	8,240	E 3	8,050	E 1	8,130	E 1	8,210	E 3	8,380	E 1	8,340
E 1	7,820	E 7	7,660	A 11	7,490	F 8	6,990	E 4	6,390	X 12	4,080	X 15	6,500	A 7	7,070	A 5	7,540
A 5	7,340	A 7	7,400	E 7	7,660	F 6	7,000	A 8	7,490	X 15	4,660	A 3	6,730	A 7	7,210	E 2	7,980
F 11	17,730	E 3	23,210	E 2	24,100	X 18	13,270	F 15	13,640	X 16	18,950	F 7	19,160	A 9	20,840	A 7	21,800
E 3	22,950	E 2	23,350	E 2	24,270	X 18	13,390	F 14	19,110	X 17	11,820	F 6	19,850	A 8	21,250	A 5	22,100
X 12	14,950	E 6	20,640	A 7	20,920	F 14	17,700	F 14	17,300	F 7	16,610	F 6	17,810	F 11	18,440	A 8	19,450
X 12	14,910	E 4	20,580	E 5	21,000	F 11	16,970	F 11	18,040	F 7	16,800	F 7	17,640	F 12	18,540	A 8	19,380
X 13	18,300	F 16	22,310	F 17	22,050	X 16	17,970	F 16	20,720	X 14	14,430	F 5	22,850	F 16	20,930	F 13	19,990
X 13	17,680	F 16	21,110	F 16	22,440	X 17	15,260	X 16	19,010	X 16	13,990	X 11	18,490	A 11	23,580	A 7	24,050
X 15	7,520	X 18	7,330	X 18	7,470	X 17	7,130	X 17	7,810	X 10	8,010	F 10	9,350	F 17	9,160	F 10	9,750
X 14	7,410	X 18	7,210	X 18	7,490	X 16	7,330	X 17	8,000	X 11	7,990	X 12	8,250	A 9	10,740	A 9	10,670
X 17	4,070	A 12	7,960	E 1	8,800	F 11	7,000	X 18	4,530	F 9	6,300	X 13	4,170	F 13	6,910	X 16	5,050
X 15	4,140	A 6	7,920	E 1	8,770	F 9	7,010	X 18	4,320	X 9	5,920	X 13	5,640	F 16	6,610	X 15	2,410
E 3	15,810	E 9	15,680	E 6	15,970	E 3	15,820	E 3	16,050	E 3	15,620	F 4	14,400	A 8	14,780	F 12	12,750
E 1	16,000	E 3	15,780	E 6	15,950	E 3	15,580	E 2	16,340	A 3	15,460	F 5	14,210	A 9	14,560	F 10	13,170
E 5	18,720	E 10	19,080	A 14	18,290	A 4	18,530	A 9	18,500	F 5	16,630	A 3	17,800	E 6	18,950	E 3	19,680
A 8	17,760	A 9	18,410	E 8	19,130	A 4	18,620	E 5	19,270	F 5	15,800	A 4	17,800	E 5	19,210	A 4	18,780
E 2	20,850	E 5	20,940	A 15	19,170	E 2	21,360	E 1	21,480	X 12	14,070	X 17	D	E 3	21,150	E 4	20,850
E 1	21,000	F 15	17,120	F 17	16,280	E 1	22,680	E 1	21,690	X 14	13,440	X 16	D	E 2	22,050	F 11	16,800

E = Excellent: 0 to 3% loss of tensile strength.
A = Acceptable: 3 to 10% loss of tensile strength.
F = Fair: 10 to 25% loss of tensile strength.
X = Unacceptable: more than 25% loss of tensile strength.
C = Sample crazed or cracked.
D = Sample dissolved or severely tackified.

compound is judged unacceptable in methanol with a tensile strength of 13,360 psi. Subjected to 1/4% strain, the additional loss is nearly 50% to 7600 psi.

The primary effect of most chemical environments on polymers or composites is through their action as a solvent. Solvent effects are functions of polarity and viscosity. (Consideration must also be made of melting and boiling temperatures.) If the polarity of a solvent matches that of primary polymer bond, the loss in mechanical properties is greater than in other solvents. Thus, a close match represents an incompatible service environment for a given polymer. Selection of a polymer for a given environment should be made by choosing the material farthest from a polarity match with the solvent environment. Inspection of Table 3 indicates that glass reinforced nylon 6/6 is resistant to typical cleaning solvents such as carbon tetrachloride and that glass reinforced polystyrene is unsuitable for exposure to antifreeze (ethylene glycol). Methanol (wood alcohol) of similar polarity but reduced viscosity would be expected to have even a greater deleterious effect on the styrene material. Both of these conclusions are supported by Tables 1 and 2.

A pure solvent generally has less effect on a polymer or composite than an impure solvent or a mixture of solvents. Gasoline, for example, has a greater effect than hexane.

In almost all cases, glass reinforced thermoplastic resins have greater chemical resistance than the unreinforced polymer. Initially, mechanical properties of composites far

exceed those of the unreinforced polymer. Thus, even if percent losses in strength were equivalent, the composite would still have greater strength after exposure. Actually, however, percent strength losses of the composites are generally less than those of the unreinforced polymer.

Composites that are closest to optimum theoretical reinforcement have the best chemical resistance. Production of such composites involves the physiochemical linking of the polymer to the glass fibers. Thus, the resin is tightly bonded in a matrix which does not allow interpenetration of a solvent that could associate more strongly with the resin than the resin associates with the glass.

Hydrolysis Resistance

Both the cause and method of failure for glass reinforced thermoplastics exposed to water vary widely. No glass reinforced thermoplastic resin simply dissolves in water. Calorimetric data have indicated that even on a microscopic level, the chemical interaction of water molecules (solvation) does not occur. Thus, the commonly encountered modes of failure for glass reinforced thermoplastic—swelling, stress cracking, and wicking, like the failure of their unreinforced counterparts, must be accounted for by the physical presence of water molecules, ionic (salt) impurities, dissolved air, and bacteria.

Water transport throughout a thermoplastic article may be broken into two processes—sorption and diffusion. Sorption is the entrance of the water molecules into the

TABLE 3 – Environmental Comparator

		Dielectric Constant of Solvent										
		78.4	48.9	44.0	37.7	32.6	24.3	20.7	4.3	2.0	2.3	
		Chemical Environment										
		Strong	Weak									
Sulfuric Acid	Acids Bases Salts	Water	Dimethyl Sulfoxide	Benzene	Ethylene Glycol	Methanol	Ethanol	Acetone	Ethyl Ether	Gasoline	Hep-tane	Carbon Tetrachloride
		Base Resin										
Nylon ⁴	Polyurethane ^{4, 5}	Polyester		Polycarbonate ³	Polysulfone ^{3, 7}	Polystyrene ^{1, 6}		Polyacetal ²	Polypropylene Polyethylene Polyvinyl Chloride			
Nylon 6/6	Nylon 6/12	Nylon 12						Noryl				

Note: Polymers with the most resistance to a given chemical environment are farthest from that chemical in the scale above. (A polymer has no resistance to the chemical directly above it.)

Exceptions to these general compatibility rules are (as indicated by superscripts above): 1. organic acids, 2. sulfuric acid, 3. bases, 4. alcohol, 5. glycols, 6. oxidizing solutions, and 7. automotive fluids.

resin. Diffusion is the distribution by random molecular motion throughout the resin. If the water contact is a vapor, the equilibrium water absorption is a function of the relative humidity. Relative humidity is a measure of partial pressure specific for water vapor. At low partial pressures, there is a linear dependence of water absorption and consequent dimensional change in accordance with Henry's Law: concentration of water within thermoplastic = constant X partial pressure.

Variations from the ideal situation are due to the absence of highly diffusible unimolecular water as a result of molecular clusters of water formed at higher concentrations and site effects of coordination around the amide bond in nylons. Site effects encountered in nylons, polyesters, polyurethanes, and polycarbonates account for the dramatic changes in physical properties when dry molded material is moisture conditioned.

When a thermoplastic is placed in an aqueous environment, the effects of water are more rapid. The attainment of equilibrium is controlled to a greater degree by sorption. Sorption becomes a direct function of water contact or wetting. No thermoplastic is wet-out completely by water since the surface tension of water (72.5 dynes/cm) is too high. However, as the surface tension increases, the polymer becomes less hydrolytically stable.

Polymers with lower critical surface tension have fewer reactive groups. Thus, 30% glass fortified PPO, polysulfone, and polypropylene exhibit outstanding long term resistance in 100 C water. (Polyethylene is eliminated here because of temperature, not because of hydrolytic stability.) The 30% glass fortified nylon 6/10, modified PPO, and PVC exhibit intermediate resistance to 100 C water. Although glass reinforced nylons remain the least hydrolytically stable due to their bond hydrolysis, a dramatic increase in resistance has been accomplished when compared to the neat nylon resins.

The reduction in water absorption and dimensional change values for glass fortified nylon resins exceed those expected for a simple replacement of the neat resin by glass fibers. This can be explained by postulating a greater affinity of the nylon resin amide groups for the glass fiber sizing systems than for water. Another peculiar feature of glass reinforced nylon resins is the reduction in stress cracking. If an unreinforced nylon is contacted by a high salt content solution, cracks develop perpendicular to the direction of applied stress in the sample; 50% zinc chloride

solution will produce cracks in less than 45 minutes. The mechanism of this stress cracking is at present unexplained, but glass reinforcement apparently mitigates the effect by transferring stress along the glass fibers rather than along the resin.

Glass reinforced resins contain coupling agents that bond to the resin and thus exclude interaction of water molecules, lending stability to the composites. While the silanol bond between the coupling agent and the glass is hydrolyzed, the negligible permeation by the coupling agent and the dynamic reverse formation of the silanol bond results in maintenance of physical properties by most composites far in excess of those expected from the neat resin. In highly permeable resins, a greater degree of hydrolysis occurs along the fibers, and wicking may be observed. Under long term conditions, 30% glass reinforced acetal and polysulfone are hydrolyzed to such a degree that the composites have less stability than the neat resin.

A relative ranking of long term hydrolytic aging of the series of 30% glass fortified thermoplastic resins tested is polypropylene > polysulfone > PPO > modified PPO > PVC > nylon 6/10 > polyacetal > SAN > polycarbonate. The test method provided for both a hydrolytic and an oxidative attack. The oxygen content of the water was maintained by changing it weekly in test flasks.

The 24-hr water absorption at 23 C ranged from 0.02% for PVC to 0.25% for polyacetal; the saturation values ranged from 0.11% for modified PPO to 1.85% for nylon 6/10. The absorption values in 100 C water exhibited a range from 0.40% from modified PPO to 5.41% for PVC after immersion for 5000 hrs. The reverse in absorption characteristics (short term vs long term) in PVC is not only accounted for by wetting characteristics but by the leaching of stabilizers and subsequent replacement with water.

Conclusions

1. The addition of glass fiber reinforcement can significantly improve the chemical resistance of thermoplastic resins.

2. Glass reinforced thermoplastic resins exhibit a greater improvement in chemical resistance in nonaqueous environments.

3. Glass reinforced thermoplastic resins exhibit improved long term hydrolytic stability when compared with the base resins.